

1 **DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A GREEN ANALYTICAL METHOD**
2 **FOR DETERMINING FOURTEEN BISPHENOLS IN BEE POLLEN BY**
3 **ULTRA-HIGH-PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY-TANDEM**
4 **MASS SPECTROMETRY**

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15 **Abstract**

16 A new analytical method was developed and validated to determine fourteen bisphenols
17 (A, B, C, E, F, M, P, S, Z, AF, AP, BP, FL, PH) in bee pollen using ultra-high-performance
18 liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. Two different sample treatments were
19 proposed and evaluated: one based on the QuEChERS (quick, easy, cheap, effective,
20 rugged & safe) approach and the other utilizing microextraction with a supramolecular
21 solvent (SUPRAS). In both cases, average analyte recovery ranged between 71% and
22 114%, and the matrix effect was between -45% and +5%, although it was not significant
23 when using the QuEChERS-based method ($\leq \pm 20\%$). The environmental impact of both
24 sample treatments was assessed using different analytical metrics, with both procedures
25 classified as environmentally friendly, though slightly better results were obtained for
26 SUPRAS. The method was fully validated, showing that the QuEChERS approach had
27 better overall performance, particularly regarding sensitivity and matrix effect.
28 Consequently, the QuEChERS methodology was applied to determine bisphenols in thirty
29 bee pollen samples from different Spanish regions. Residues of three bisphenols (M, P,
30 and S) were detected, although only bisphenol S was quantified in several samples at low
31 concentration levels ($< 7 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), which is below the established specific migration limit
32 (SML; $50 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). However, regarding human health, the estimated daily intake, target
33 hazard quotient, and hazard index assessed were higher than acceptable limits, suggesting
34 a potential risk for human consumers.

35 **Keywords:** Bee pollen; Bisphenols; Food analysis; Food Safety; Green analytical
36 chemistry; Method validation; Risk assessment, Sample treatment; UHPLC-MS/MS

37 **1. Introduction**

38 Bee pollen has proved to be a highly demanded food by society due to both its health-
39 promoting effects (anticancer, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant) and its nutritional
40 properties (Ares, Valverde, Bernal, Nozal, & Bernal, 2018). However, aside from being a
41 functional food for human health, it is also essential for bee nutrition. Honeybees and
42 beehive products, like bee pollen, have been shown to be bioindicators of numerous
43 pollutants sources coming from agricultural and industrial activities such as pesticides,
44 insecticides, and heavy metals (Cabrera de Oliveira, Queiroz, Pinto da Luz, Silveira Porto,
45 & Rath, 2016; Fuente-Ballesteros et al., 2023; Valverde et al., 2018). In recent years, there
46 has been a significant increase in plastic production, reaching approximately 400 million
47 tons annually in 2022 (PlasticsEurope, 2023). Nevertheless, despite its usefulness and
48 ubiquity, current patterns of plastic consumption and disposal are contributing to
49 substantial pollution in the environment (Heidbreder, Bablok, Drews, & Menzel, 2019).
50 One notable contributor to this pollution is the use of additives, commonly known as
51 plasticizers, aimed at enhancing the properties of plastics. One of the most employed
52 plastic additives is bisphenol A (BPA), which belongs to the group of bisphenols that are
53 phenolic compounds used both to produce polycarbonate and epoxy resins (Loganathan
54 et al., 2023). BPA is considered as an endocrine disruptor with estrogenic activity even at
55 low concentrations, meaning that BPA can bind estrogen receptors causing a disruption
56 of hormonal activity, hence leading to negative health effects (Grignard, Lapenna, &
57 Bremmer, 2012). However, BPA is currently being replaced by its less well-studied and
58 regulated analogues. Some of them are bisphenol S (BPS), bisphenol F (BPF), bisphenol
59 AP (BPAP), bisphenol AF (BPAF), bisphenol C (BPC), bisphenol E (BPE), bisphenol Z
60 (BPZ), bisphenol B (BPB), phenol BPPH (BPFL), bisphenol BPFL (BPFL), bisphenol
61 BP (BPBP), bisphenol P (BPP) and bisphenol M (BPM). The European Commission has

62 established specific migration limits (SMLs) for bisphenol A (BPA) from varnishes or
63 coatings into food at 0.05 mg kg⁻¹ of food. Additionally, the use of BPA is prohibited in
64 articles intended for infants and young children (European Commission, 2018). Currently,
65 no SMLs have been set for BPA analogues, except for bisphenol S (BPS), which also has
66 an SML of 0.05 mg kg⁻¹ (European Commission, 2011). It is important to note that the
67 existing legislation applies these SMLs uniformly across all types of food without
68 differentiation. Given the high-fat content of bee pollen, there is a higher likelihood for
69 these compounds to accumulate, increasing the potential exposure for consumers
70 (Palsania, Singhal, Dar, & Kaushik, 2024).

71 To our knowledge, only one work dedicated to the analysis of BPs in pollen has been
72 published (Zhang et al., 2021). In this work, an analytical method that consisted of a
73 sample treatment based on micro salting-out assisted matrix solid-phase dispersion (μ -
74 SOA-MSPD) followed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) was
75 proposed for determining BPA and BPB in Chinese bee pollen samples. Current methods
76 for determining BPs in food are predominantly based on chromatographic techniques
77 such as HPLC or gas chromatography (GC), although HPLC is used more frequently than
78 GC, as expected, to avoid the need for a derivatization step (Martín-Gómez, Elmore,
79 Valverde, Ares, & Bernal, 2024a). HPLC can be coupled with FLD and diode array
80 detectors (DAD), which offer advantages such as simplicity and low cost. However, to
81 improve selectivity and sensitivity when analyzing BPs at low concentrations in a
82 complex matrix, like bee pollen, it is more convenient to use mass spectrometry (MS) and
83 tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS; Martínez-Gómez, Valverde, Bernal, & Ares, 2024b)
84 detectors. Regarding the stationary phase, C₁₈-based columns are commonly used for
85 determining BPs in food (Martínez-Gómez et al., 2024a) including the only known study
86 on this matrix (Zhang et al., 2021). In relation to the sample treatment and given the lack

87 of specific approaches for determining BPs in bee pollen, except for the above-mentioned
88 study, it was decided to evaluate the performance of some methodologies used in other
89 fatty matrices (Luo et al., 2017), and the research group's experience to propose the most
90 suitable procedure. One of these methods is QuEChERS (quick, easy, cheap, effective,
91 rugged, and safe) due to its simplicity, speed, high sample throughput, and versatility in
92 extracting both polar and non-polar compounds. Furthermore, it has exhibited satisfactory
93 performance in extracting other contaminants in bee pollen (Fuente-Ballesteros, Augé,
94 Bernal, & Ares, 2023). However, given the current trend in sample preparation
95 techniques, which emphasizes simplification to reduce time, costs, and the number of
96 reagents, the QuEChERS's performance was compared with that obtained using
97 supramolecular solvents (SUPRAS). SUPRAS are considered as a promising alternative
98 to conventional solvents/sample treatments, especially for its ability to significantly
99 reduce phospholipid-based matrix effects (Salatti-Dorado, Caballero-Casero, Sicilia,
100 Lunar, & Rubio, 2017).

101

102 The main goal of this study is to develop a method for the simultaneous determination of
103 fourteen bisphenols (BPA, BPAF, BPAP, BPB, BPBP, BPC, BPE, BPF, BPFL, BPM, BPP,
104 BPPH, BPS, and BPZ) in bee pollen using ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography
105 coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS). Additionally, the study aims
106 to propose a sample treatment that is efficient, simple, cost-effective, and rapid. These
107 conditions aim to ensure high recoveries, minimize potential matrix effects, and align
108 with the principles of green analytical chemistry (Gałuszka, Migaszewski, & Namieśnik,
109 2013) by reducing time, cost, steps, and reagent use, and avoiding derivatization
110 procedures. To achieve these goals, the study evaluates two sample treatment approaches:
111 SUPRAS and QuEChERS. It also includes an assessment of the environmental impact of

112 these treatments using green analytical metrics. To the best of our knowledge, this is the
113 first study to develop and optimize a UHPLC-MS/MS method for analyzing many
114 bisphenols in bee pollen. It represents the most comprehensive examination of bisphenols
115 in this matrix to date. Further objectives include validating the method according to
116 current European guidelines (EURACHEM, 2014), analyzing bee pollen samples from
117 various Spanish regions, and evaluating potential risks to consumer health.

118

119 **2. Materials and methods**

120 2.1. Reagents and materials

121 BPs standards (BPA, BPA-d₁₆, BPAF, BPAP, BPB, BPBP, BPC, BPE, BPF, BPFL, BPM,
122 BPP, BPPH, BPS, BPZ; see structures in Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**), all of
123 analytical-grade and with purity greater than 98%, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich
124 Chemie Gbmh (Steinheim, Germany). All solvents and reagents were of
125 chromatographic/analytical grade and obtained from Scharlab S.L. (Barcelona, Spain)
126 chloroform from Lab Scan Ltd. (Dublin, Ireland), acetone, methanol, ethanol,
127 tetrahydrofuran and acetonitrile from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie Gbmh (Steinheim,
128 Germany); 1-hexanol, 1-octanol, 1-dodecanol, formic acid, nitric acid, magnesium
129 sulfate, sodium chloride, ammonium acetate from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain), ,, primary
130 secondary amine (PSA), graphitized carbon black (GCB), and C₁₈ were provided by
131 Supelco (Bellefonte, CA, USA). Ultrapure water was obtained using Millipore Milli-RO
132 plus and Milli-Q systems (Bedford, MA, USA). A vortex mechanical mixer from
133 Heidolph (Schwabach, Germany), a thermostated ultrasound bath, a vibromatic
134 mechanical shaker, and a drying oven, all supplied by J.P. Selecta S.A. (Barcelona, Spain),
135 IKA[®] Ultra-Turrax[®] T18 basic disperser (IKA[®]-Werke GmbH & Co. KG, Staufen,
136 Germany), a 5810 R refrigerated bench-top centrifuge from Eppendorf (Hamburg,

137 Germany), a R-3 rotary evaporator from Buchi (Flawil, Switzerland), and Nylon syringe
138 filters (13 mm, 0.22 μm ; Branchia, Barcelona, Spain) were employed for sample
139 treatment.

140

141 To prevent cross-contamination since BPs are commonly present in reagents, materials,
142 and laboratory equipment, a meticulous cleaning protocol was required (Martín-Gómez
143 et al., 2014). Initially, glassware underwent soaking in ultrapure water, followed by
144 washing with 0.2 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid and sonication for 20 minutes. Afterwards, the
145 material was rinsed with the following solutions: **i**) ultrapure water, and the ultrasonic
146 process was repeated; **ii**) it was cleaned with an acetone and methanol (1:1, v/v) mixture;
147 **iii**) finally, it was dried at 100°C for 1 hour and covered with aluminum foil. All materials
148 were previously tested before each analysis. Procedural blanks, in which ultrapure water
149 substituted bee pollen, were run between sets of samples to monitor potential abnormal
150 background values.

151

152 2.2. Standards

153 Individual standard stock solutions for each bisphenol and the internal standard (BPA-
154 d₁₆) were prepared at a concentration of 1000 mg L⁻¹ in methanol. These stock solutions
155 were then combined and diluted with a 50:50 (v/v) mixture of deionized water and
156 methanol to prepare an intermediate mixed solution and the working solutions. Blank
157 (analyte-free; see **subsection 2.3.1**) bee pollen samples, were either spiked before (BF
158 samples) or after (AF samples) sample treatment with varying amounts of the BPs and
159 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of the IS (BPA-d₁₆) to prepare the matrix-matched standards. These samples
160 were used for validation (spiked samples (low, medium, and high) and calibration curves),

161 as well as for sample treatment studies. It is important to note that three replicates, which
162 were injected three times, were prepared for all the above-mentioned studies Each spiked
163 sample was prepared by spiking bee pollen product with three different concentrations of
164 BPs within the linear range. These concentrations were as follows: low–limit of
165 quantification (LOQ) $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (from 1.0 to 23 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$;see **Table 1**); medium–50 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$;
166 high–250 μgkg^{-1} . The stock solutions and matrix-matched solutions were stored in
167 opaque glass containers at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 4°C , respectively. All solutions demonstrated
168 stability for a period exceeding two weeks.

169

170 2.3. Sample procurement and treatment

171 2.3.1. *Samples*

172 Several bee pollen samples ($n = 30$) were selected according to their botanical origin,
173 food packaging and composition. Half of the samples were kindly donated by the Center
174 for Agroenvironmental and Apicultural Investigation (CIAPA; Marchamalo, Guadalajara,
175 Spain), and correspond to samples labeled with the letter E (E1-E15). The rest of the
176 samples were acquired from commercial stores from different geographical areas of Spain
177 labeled with the letter C (C1-C15). Their botanical origin was confirmed by palynological
178 analysis at CIAPA (Ares et al., 2022; see Supplementary Material, **Table 2S**). All the
179 samples were dried at $45\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in an oven, individually ground in a mill, and subsequently
180 stored in a vacuum desiccator before analysis. In the present study, all bee pollen samples
181 were examined in triplicate and underwent a preliminary analysis by UHPLC–MS/MS to
182 check for the presence of BPs. Once absence was confirmed in the samples (blank or
183 analyte-free), different subsamples were generated and used to prepare matrix-matched
184 standards for validation and sample treatment studies

185 2.3.2. *Sample treatment*

186 2.3.2.1. SUPRAS

187 Briefly, 1 g ± 0.1 mg of ground and dried bee pollen was weighed into a 10 mL glass tube.
188 Then, 4 mL of tetrahydrofuran, 1-hexanol and water (30:5:65, v/v/v) mixture, and 50 mg
189 of ammonium acetate were added. The mixture was vigorously shaken for 30 seconds
190 using a vortex device, and then centrifuged for 5 min (7000 g, 10°C). The SUPRAS phase
191 was collected using a syringe and evaporated to dryness under a nitrogen stream. The
192 resulting dry residue was reconstituted with 500 µL of an internal standard (IS) solution
193 (100 µg L⁻¹), and subsequently filtered through a nylon 0.22-µm filter into a vial for
194 UHPLC-MS/MS analysis. **Figure 1A** summarizes the steps of the selected sample
195 treatment.

196 2.3.2.2. QuEChERS

197 Briefly, 1 g ± 0.1 mg of ground and dried bee pollen was weighed in a 10 mL glass
198 centrifuge tube, and 8 mL of an acetonitrile and water (70:30, v/v) mixture, 150 mg of
199 ammonium acetate and 150 mg of anhydrous magnesium sulfate were added. The mixture
200 was mechanically shaken for 5 min (950 oscillations/min) in a vibromatic, and then
201 centrifuged for 5 min (7000 g, 10°C). The supernatant was collected and transferred to
202 another glass tube containing 50 mg of PSA. The tube was shaken and centrifuged using
203 the same conditions described above. Then, supernatant was collected evaporated to
204 dryness at 60°C in a rotary evaporator. Finally, the dry residue was reconstituted with 1
205 mL of IS solution (100 µg L⁻¹) and it was filtered through a nylon 0.22 µm filter into a
206 vial for UHPLC-MS/MS analysis. **Figure 1B** summarizes the steps of the selected sample
207 treatment.

208

209 2.4. UHPLC-MS/MS conditions

210 Analyses were carried out using an UHPLC Sciex Exion system connected to a Sciex
211 6500+ triple-quadrupole mass spectrometer from Sciex (Washington, DC, USA)
212 equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source, which was used in negative mode.
213 UHPLC-MS/MS conditions were optimized in a previous and recent work (Martín-
214 Gómez et al., 2024b). Chromatographic separation was accomplished using a reversed
215 phase column, Kinetex EVO C₁₈ (2.1 mm × 50 mm, 1.7 μm), protected with a Kinetex
216 EVO C₁₈ guard column, both from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA). Mobile phase was
217 composed of 10 mM ammonium acetate in ultrapure water (solvent A) and methanol
218 (solvent B) at a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min in the following gradient mode: (i) 0.0 min (A–
219 B, 50:50, v/v); (ii) 1.0 min (A–B, 50:50, v/v); (iii) 5.0 min (A–B, 15:85, v/v); (iv) 11.0
220 min (A–B, 15:85, v/v); (v) 13.0 min (A–B, 50:50, v/v); (vi) 15.0 min (A–B, 50:50, v/v).
221 Temperature and injection volume was set at 30°C and 3 μL, respectively. With such
222 conditions, the overall run time was 15 min (see **Figure 2**). MS/MS conditions were
223 optimized by flow injection analysis in infusion mode of each BP standard at 20 μL min⁻¹.
224 The ESI operational settings were as follows: capillary voltage, -4500 V; capillary
225 temperature, 300 °C; ion source gas 1 and 2 pressure, 80 psi and 60 psi, respectively;
226 curtain gas, 35 psi; collision gas, 9 psi. For mass spectrometry acquisition, multiple
227 reaction monitoring (MRM) mode was employed. This mode recorded the transitions
228 between the precursor ion and the most abundant product ions for each target analyte (see
229 conditions and transitions in **Table 2**). Two transitions were selected for each target
230 analyte to enhance the specificity and reliability of the analysis, and to minimize the risk
231 of false positives. Dwell times were automatically chosen to ensure an adequate number
232 of data points for each peak. SciexOS software was employed for data acquisition and
233 evaluation
234

235 **3. Results and discussion**

236 3.1. Optimization of sample treatment

237 *3.1.1. SUPRAS*

238 Firstly, the use of SUPRAS was examined, as it can be considered an interesting non-
239 conventional solvent extraction to be used as an alternative to organic solvents, such as
240 acetonitrile that was used in the only work where BPs have been determined in bee pollen
241 (Zhang et al., 2021). SUPRAS offers advantages such as high enrichment factors, low
242 solvent consumption, and rapid extraction. Furthermore, recent SUPRAS-based studies
243 have been published reporting satisfactory results in terms of extraction efficiency and
244 the influence of matrix effects when analyzing BPs and other plasticizers in other matrices
245 (Ballesteros-Gómez, Ballesteros, & Rubio, 2024; Dueñas-Mas, Ballesteros-Gómez, &
246 Rubio, 2022). The formation of SUPRAS involves two consecutive steps. Initially, three-
247 dimensional aggregates, typically micelles or vesicles, spontaneously form through the
248 self-assembly of amphiphilic compounds upon reaching a critical micellar/vesicular
249 concentration. Subsequently, these aggregates suffer an expansion by the influence of a
250 coacervating agent, such as a pH or temperature change, addition of a salt or a poor
251 solvent for the amphiphile (Dueñas-Mas, de Dios-Pérez, Ballesteros-Gómez, & Rubio,
252 2023). This process results in the formation of three phases during extraction, the solid
253 residue, the equilibrium solution and the creation of a new liquid phase enrichment
254 denominated SUPRAS. SUPRAS solutions were previously synthesized from ternary
255 mixtures of 10 mL containing amphiphile (5% v/v), organic solvent (10-30%, v/v) and
256 water (60-85%, v/v; Alabi, Caballero-Casero, & Rubio, 2014). Considering the
257 proportions used in other studies, the initial SUPRAS volume was set at 2 mL and the
258 sample amount was fixed at 50 mg. Then, the obtained solutions were shaken for 30 s in
259 a vortex device, and centrifuged (5 min, 7000 g, 10°C) to accelerate phase separation.

260 Several amphiphiles substances (1-hexanol, 1-octanol and 1-decanol) and two organic
261 solvents (aprotic-tetrahydrofuran; protic-ethanol) were tested, and ultra-pure water was
262 selected as coacervating agent (see the synthesized SUPRAS solutions in **Table 3S**,
263 Supplementary Material). In general, better results with higher recovery percentages were
264 achieved using tetrahydrofuran as organic solvent (data not shown). It was also observed
265 that a great dependence of the formation of the SUPRAS phase with the tetrahydrofuran
266 and water ratio in the different solutions tested. Regarding the amphiphilic substance, a
267 general trend was observed, as the hydrocarbon chain length increased, more turbid and
268 dense phases were obtained. This phenomenon may be attributed to the co-extraction of
269 lipids, as bee pollen could reach up to 15% w/w of its content (Ares et al., 2018). The best
270 results were achieved with 1-hexanol and tetrahydrofuran, where the formation of the
271 SUPRAS phase was observed. This finding is in good concordance with those reported
272 in other studies, predominating amphiphile-amphiphile interactions over amphiphile-
273 solvent interactions (Caballero-Casero, & Rubio, 2021). Once the composition of the
274 SUPRAS phase was selected (THF 30%, 1-hexanol 5%, water 65%; v/v), the next steps
275 involved the selection of the SUPRAS volume (0.5-5.0 mL) and the amount of the sample
276 (50-2000 mg). After performing several tests, 1000 mg and 4 mL of SUPRAS solvent
277 were deemed as optimal values in terms of extraction recovery (55-70% for all BPs),
278 although a significant matrix effect (signal suppression) was observed for most
279 compounds (data not shown). Then, to improve the coacervation process and thereby
280 improve the extraction efficiency of BPs, the effect pH adjustment and salt addition were
281 evaluated. Considering that the pKa values of the BPs are comprised between 9 and 11
282 (Chen et al., 2022), experiments were conducted at acidic pH values (2 and 3), but in both
283 cases, it was observed that SUPRAS phase could not be clearly distinguished.
284 Consequently, it was concluded that controlling pH did not improve the SUPRAS

285 procedure. Thus, the effect of salt addition was subsequently investigated by using
286 different salts (50 mg) like sodium acetate, sodium chloride and magnesium sulfate. The
287 recovery efficiency increased in all cases, being ammonium acetate the salt that provided
288 the highest recovery percentages (65-110%) for all BPs with an acceptable matrix effect
289 (see Supplementary Material, **Figure 1S**). Next, the amount of ammonium acetate (25,
290 50, 100 y 150 mg) was optimized. It was observed that when the minimum amount of salt
291 was used (25 mg), there was no improvement in the recovery efficiency. On the contrary,
292 when higher quantities were tested (50-150 mg), quite similar results were obtained in
293 terms of recovery percentages and matrix effect (data not shown). Therefore, the lowest
294 quantity (50 mg) was selected to continue the optimization process. The influence of
295 extraction (30-90 s) and centrifugation times (3–10 min) was also investigated. The
296 results showed that the best recovery percentages (> 70%) were obtained with 30 s of
297 vortex agitation, followed by 5 min of centrifugation. Finally, the SUPRAS phase (~80
298 μL) was collected with a syringe and evaporated to dryness under a nitrogen stream.
299 Several methanol and water mixtures (50:50, 70:30, 80:20; 100:0 v/v) and volumes (100–
300 1000 μL) were tested to dissolve the dry extract. It was observed that 500 μL of a 50:50
301 v/v mixture provided the best results in terms of extraction efficiency and matrix effect
302 (data not shown).

303 *3.1.2. QuEChERS*

304 The first step of the optimization procedure was devoted to select the amount of bee pollen
305 (0.5–2 g). Several tests were conducted to optimize the extraction process. Initially, it was
306 determined that 1.0 g of bee pollen was the maximum amount needed to achieve optimal
307 signal-to-noise ratios, which provided the best sensitivity (data not shown). Next,
308 different solvent mixtures of acetonitrile and water (60:40, 70:30, 80:20, 90:10 v/v) were
309 evaluated based on existing literature (Martín-Gómez et al., 2024a). The best extraction

310 efficiency was obtained with a mixture of acetonitrile and water 70:30 (v/v). Following
311 this, different volumes (4-10 mL) of the selected solvent mixture were tested, with 8 mL
312 being identified as the optimal volume. Additionally, the effect of various salts (sodium
313 chloride, magnesium sulfate, ammonium acetate) on the partitioning step of the
314 QuEChERS procedure was investigated. The highest recovery percentages (> 70%) were
315 achieved when employing 150 mg of magnesium sulfate and 150 mg of ammonium
316 acetate. Once the solvents and the salts were chosen, the influence of various extraction
317 parameters was also examined. This involved the influence of agitation source
318 (vibromatic, ultrasound and Ultra-Turrax[®]), extraction time (3–15 min), and
319 centrifugation time (3–15 min), which were sequentially tested. Optimal extraction
320 conditions were achieved with 5 min of mechanical agitation (vibromatic), and 5 min of
321 centrifugation (7000 g , 10 °C). Then, the feasibility of a clean-up step to remove co-
322 extracted interfering substances and minimize the matrix effect was evaluated. The
323 supernatant was collected and transferred to a glass tube, in which PSA, C₁₈, GCB, and a
324 mixture of them in combination with magnesium sulfate were added in different
325 experiments with the aim of removing sugars, fatty acids (PSA) and non-polar
326 compounds (C₁₈, GCB). Different amounts of sorbents were also tested (50-500 mg), and
327 it was observed that 50 mg PSA provided the optimum efficiency in terms of minimizing
328 matrix effect (< ± 20%) without affecting the extraction efficiency (recovery percentages
329 higher than 70%; see **Table 4S**). The other evaluated sorbents induced a significant loss
330 of some analytes, especially in the case of GCB. It should be mentioned that the shaking
331 and centrifugation conditions for the clean-up step were the same as those used for the
332 extraction stage. The supernatant was directly transferred to a conical flask and gently
333 evaporated to dryness in a rotary evaporator at 60°C. Different volumes (0.5–2.0 mL) of
334 methanol and water (90:10, 80:20, 70:30, 60:40, 50:50, v/v) mixtures were tested to

335 dissolve the dry extract. It was observed that 1 mL of a 70:30 (v/v) mixture provided the
336 best results in terms of extraction efficiency and matrix effect (data not shown).

337 *3.1.3. Comparison of the proposed sample treatments*

338 In order to check the effectiveness of the proposed sample treatments, BPs responses
339 (analyte peak area/IS area) obtained from blank samples spiked at three different
340 concentrations (low-LOQ (see **Table 1**); medium-50 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$; and high-250 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) were
341 compared, both prior to (BF samples) or following (AF samples) sample treatment were
342 compared. The extraction efficiency ranged from 75% to 114% using the QuEChERS
343 approach; while these values were slightly lower when using SUPRAS solvent between
344 71% to 103% (see **Table 3**). Regarding the evaluation of the matrix effect, calculated as
345 outlined in **subsection 3.4.3**, a significant signal suppression was observed for six BPs
346 (BPA, BPE, BPF, BPM, BPPH and BPS) at the three spiked concentration when
347 employing the SUPRAS approach (see **Table 3**). This result implies that standard matrix
348 calibration curves should be required for quantifying these compounds by using
349 SUPRAS. In contrast, the QuEChERS approach provided suitable matrix effect values
350 for all studied BPs and spiking levels, indicating that standard in solvent calibration
351 curves could be used to quantify BPs in bee pollen. On the other hand, it must also be
352 considered that the method based on SUPRAS is faster, has fewer steps, and requires less
353 solvent consumption, although due to the instrumentation used, fewer samples can be
354 treated simultaneously. Finally, if we compare the proposed sample treatments (SUPRAS
355 and QuEChERS) with the only existing one (μ -SOA-MSPD; Zhang et al., 2021), it is
356 observed that the performances in terms of recovery percentages are very similar in all
357 cases, although they were slightly better for the QuEChERS. It should be remarked that
358 the effect of the matrix on the ionization of the BPs was not studied in the previous
359 method. On the other hand, the analysis time, simplicity, and consumption of reagents is

360 very similar for the SUPRAS and μ -SOA-MSPD) methodologies, while as previously
361 mentioned, the QuEChERS method has more stages and reagents consumption, although
362 it has the advantage that it minimizes the matrix effect. Thus, it can be concluded that
363 both procedures can be considered as promising alternatives when determining BPs in
364 bee pollen, with the QuEChERS methodology presenting better efficiency when
365 extracting the compounds and avoiding the matrix effect, while the SUPRAS
366 methodology is faster, simpler, and requires less reagent consumption.

367

368 3.2. Assessment of the proposed sample treatments sustainability

369 Three commonly employed tools (analytical greenness calculator (AGREE), Pena-
370 Pereira, Wojnowski, & Tobiszewski, 2020; analytical GREENness (AGREEprep) metric,
371 Pereira, Tobiszewski, Wojnowski, & Psillakis, 2022; complex green analytical procedure
372 index (ComplexGAPI), Płotka-Wasyłka, & Wojnowski, 2021) were used to assess the
373 sustainability of the proposed analytical approaches based on QuEChERS and SUPRAS.
374 AGREE is based on the twelve principles of green analytical chemistry (GAC; Gałuszka
375 et al., 2013), providing a numerical score ranging from 0 to 1. The results are represented
376 in a pictogram on a red-yellow-green color scale, with a method considered “green” when
377 the score is greater than 0.6. AGREEprep is based on ten green sample preparation (GSP)
378 principles (López-Lorente et al., 2022). The results are also based on a numerical score
379 (0-1) and are presented as a pictogram using the same color scales as in AGREE. The
380 main difference between AGREE and AGREEprep lies in the fact that the former
381 evaluates the entire analytical procedure, whereas AGREEprep focuses on sample
382 preparation. The ComplexGAPI metric provides a comprehensive overview for the entire
383 method considers a range of factors, encompassing the final product, reactants/solvents,
384 alignment with a sustainable economic framework, instrumentation, post processing, and

385 purification steps. The results are visualized through hexagons with a color-coded system.
386 Red color signifies high environmental concern, yellow indicates a moderate level of
387 concern, and green represents minimal concern. Comparison of the greenness profile of
388 both methodologies is summarized in **Table 4**. The pictograms obtained in AGREE
389 yielded a central score of 0.71 for SUPRAS, categorizing it as “green”. Meanwhile, for
390 QuEChERS methodology, it was on the threshold with a value of 0.60. In both
391 methodologies, the use of UHPLC-MS/MS as an analytical technique and the location of
392 the analytical device (points 5 and 9) have been penalized. In the case of the QuEChERS
393 methodology, there is a penalty for the non-miniaturized sample treatment, even though
394 only 8 mL of solvent is used. In the case of AGREEPrep, slightly lower results were
395 obtained for both methodologies. The weaknesses or areas more penalized were the lack
396 of automation of the sample treatment and the use of UHPLC as the analysis technique.
397 In the case of the QuEChERS methodology, the solvent volume used was also notably
398 penalized. The ComplexGAPI provides a broader perspective. In the SUPRAS case, two
399 red segments were obtained, while in QuEChERS, three were identified. Once again,
400 weaknesses were linked to the instrumentation employed. This metric penalized the
401 requirement for sample treatment, and in the case of QuEChERS, the lack of
402 miniaturization was also noted. The matrix under study is highly complex, and the
403 analytes are typically present at trace levels, requiring a sample treatment approach to
404 achieve these objectives. To attain the desired sensitivity, the UHPLC-MS/MS technique
405 is required. Furthermore, none of the available tools address the energy consumption of
406 UHPLC-MS/MS, for which these techniques are assigned with 1.5 or >1.5 kWh energy
407 utilization per sample. Finally, we decided not to include the previous work (Zhang et al.,
408 2021) in this section, since the comparison would not be carried out under equal
409 conditions. The number of studied compounds was much lower, and the technique used

410 for the analysis (HPLC-FLD) is good enough to determine the compounds and more
411 environmentally friendly than UHPLC-MS/MS, but it did not provide an adequate
412 sensitivity according to the established SMLs.

413

414 3.3. Validation of the methods

415 Validation was performed according to EURACHEM guideline (EURACHEM, 2014).

416 The specific procedures for determining the different validation parameters are
417 summarized in **Table 5S**.

418 3.3.1. Selectivity

419 Selectivity was evaluated by comparing the chromatograms and mass spectra of standards
420 in solvents and blanks of bee pollen. No matrix interferences were observed at the
421 analytes` retention times (see **Figure 2**). Moreover, we obtained similar mass spectra for
422 the standards of BPs in solvents and in the matrix extracts (data not shown).

423 3.3.2. Limits of detection and quantification

424 The limits of detection (LODs) and quantification (LOQs) were estimated to be three and
425 ten times the signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio, respectively, and they are summarized in **Table**
426 **1**. As can be seen, lower LODs and LOQs were obtained with QuEChERS methodology
427 ($0.3\text{-}14.0\ \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) compared to the SUPRAS approach ($0.6\text{-}22.4\ \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). Those values
428 are much lower than the SMLs established by legislation for BPA and BPS ($50\ \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$),
429 and that the LODs and LOQs obtained in the previous work ($20\text{-}80\ \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$; Zhang et al.,
430 2021), which demonstrates the excellent sensitivity of the proposed method.

431 3.3.3. Matrix effect

432 To ascertain how the matrix influenced the MS signal of the studied compounds, we
433 compared the detector responses (analyte peak area/IS area) of standards in matrix
434 extracts (R_{matrix} ; AF samples) and standards in solvents (R_{solvent}) of the bee pollen samples
435 spiked at three different concentrations. It was calculated using the following formula:
436 Matrix effect (%) = $[(R_{\text{matrix}}/R_{\text{solvent}}) - 1] \times 100$. Results are summarized in **Table 3**
437 for both methodologies. Analyte responses at the three levels assayed ranged between -
438 18% of signal suppression to +5% of signal enhancement when using the QuEChERS-
439 based method, while a more significant matrix effect was observed for several of the
440 studied BPs with the SUPRAS approach (BPA, BPE, BPF, BPM, BPPH and BPS), for
441 which the signal suppression was quite significant ($> 20\%$; -45% to +3%). These results
442 were confirmed by comparing the slope confidence intervals (SCIs) between standards in
443 solvent and standards in matrix extracts (see **Table 1**). When the QuEChERS
444 methodology was used, an overlap of the SCIs was observed for all BPS, while there were
445 several cases when the SUPRAS methodology was used in which there was no overlap,
446 and which coincided with the compounds already mentioned for which a significant
447 influence of the matrix on their ionization had been observed. Consequently, it can be
448 concluded that the matrix did not significantly affect the BPs signals with the QuEChERS
449 approach. On the contrary, a significant matrix effect was observed for six BPs using the
450 SUPRAS methodology, and this implies that it would be necessary to use standard in
451 matrix calibration curves for quantifying these specific compounds. In this case, a
452 comparison with the previous work in bee pollen samples cannot be made as it was not
453 used a MS detector (Zhang et al., 2021).

454 3.3.4. Working range

455 Standard in solvent calibration curves could be used to quantify BPs in all cases, except
456 BPA, BPE, BPF, BPM, BPPH and BPS that should be quantified with the standard in
457 matrix calibration curves when using the SUPRAS approach. Calibration curves ($n = 6$)
458 were constructed by plotting the signal on the y -axis (analyte peak area/IS area) against
459 analyte concentration on the x -axis. Concentration of the analytical curves varied between
460 LOQ and $250 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (LOQ (see **Table 1**), 50, 75, 100, 150, and 250), which corresponds
461 to those between LOQ and $250 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. The graphs obtained in all the calibration curves
462 were straight lines, with the coefficient of the determination values (R^2) higher than 0.99
463 in all cases (see **Table 1**). Moreover, the deviation of back-calculation concentration from
464 true concentration was lower than 15% in all cases (data not shown).

465 3.3.5. Precision studies

466 Precision was expressed as relative standard deviation (%RSD) and performed
467 concurrently by repeated sample analysis using BF samples, at three different
468 concentrations levels. These experiments took place either on the same day (repeatability)
469 or over three consecutive days (partial reproducibility). %RSD values were consistently
470 lower than 15% in all cases (see Supplementary Material, **Table 6S**). In the present study,
471 the %RSD values are slightly higher than those obtained in the previous work (<6%;
472 Zhang et al., 2021), but it should be considered that different detectors were used in each
473 case, which also influence the precision studies.

474 3.3.6. Trueness

475 Trueness was evaluated through recovery experiments by comparing the results (analyte
476 peak area/IS area) between BF samples and AF samples, which were obtained from blank
477 samples spiked at three different concentrations. Mean recoveries for the BPs studied

478 ranged in all cases from 71% to 103% (SUPRAS) or 75% to 114% (QuEChERS), with
479 %RSD values consistently below 15% in all instances these values (see **Table 3**). As it
480 has been previously mentioned in **subsection 3.1.3**, the recovery percentages obtained
481 with the proposed methods were comparable to those obtained in the previous work
482 dedicated to the analysis of BPs in bee pollen (83%-95%; Zhang et al., 2021).

483

484 3.4. Application of the method

485 The QuEChERS methodology was chosen to determine the residues of BPs in bee pollen
486 due to the lowest LOQ values provided for most compounds, and the absence of a
487 significant matrix effect. Among the fourteen BPs investigated, residues of three (BPM,
488 BPP, and BPS) were detected in fourteen of the samples (see **Table 5**), and only in one
489 sample (E2; BMP, BPP and BPS; see Supplementary Material, **Figure 2S**) was more than
490 one BPs detected. However, only BPS was quantified in twelve of the samples with
491 concentrations lower ($4\text{-}7\ \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) than the established SML ($50\ \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, European
492 Commission, 2011). It can be also concluded that most positive samples were from
493 commercial origin (71%; 10 out 14), as the number positives in samples from
494 experimental apiaries was much lower (29%, 4 out of 14). These results are relevant since
495 it is the first time that BPs residues have been detected and quantified in bee pollen
496 samples, as no BPs residues were found in the previous publication (Zhang et al., 2021).
497 It should be also highlighted that the concentrations are very similar in the samples that
498 have been quantified from both origins, and that the prevalence of samples with BPS
499 content in the experimental ones may be tentatively related either to the geographical
500 origin of the samples or to some material/procedure that has been used during their
501 collection, since they have not been treated. On the other hand, when considering the
502 packaging material, residues have been found in both plastic and glass containers,

503 although it is true that most containers were glass, which justifies the largest number of
504 positives found for this material.

505

506 3.5. Risk evaluation

507 Additionally, potential theoretical hazards associated with bee pollen samples containing
508 quantifiable levels of BPS were evaluated (see Supplementary Material, **Table 7S**). The
509 average concentration of BPS was used to calculate the Estimated Daily Intake (EDI)
510 with the formula: $EDI = CI \times DI / bw$ (Isci & Dagdemir, 2024). Here, EDI represents the
511 exposure to BPS per unit of body weight from bee pollen consumption ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ bw per
512 day), where CI is the average concentration in bee pollen samples ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), DI is the
513 recommended daily intake of bee pollen (30 g per day for adults, Sadeghi, Akhlaghi, &
514 Salehi, 2020), and bw is the reference body weight (70 kg). The TDI (Tolerable Daily
515 Intake) estimates the amount of a chemical contaminant that can be ingested daily over a
516 lifetime without significant health risks, considering environmental exposure and dietary
517 intake (EFSA, 2015). The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has established a
518 temporary TDI (t-TDI) for BPA at 0.2 ng kg^{-1} bw per day (EFSA, 2023), but no specific
519 value for BPS is available yet. Given that BPS is an analog of BPA, the BPA t-TDI was
520 used as a reference for risk assessment. The Target Hazard Quotient (THQ) was calculated
521 as $THQ = EDI / TDI$. The Hazard Index (HI), which evaluates the cumulative effect of
522 multiple hazardous elements, is the sum of the THQ values (Cunha, Inácio, Almada,
523 Ferreira, & Fernandes, 2020). However, since only BPS was quantified in this study, the
524 HI value is equivalent to the THQ value. The average EDI values ranged from 1.9 to 2.8
525 ng kg^{-1} bw per day, with slightly higher values for experimental samples. The THQ and
526 HI values ranged from 9.8 to 14.0, all exceeding the threshold value of 1. These elevated
527 values indicate a significant risk, based on EFSA's limits. Note that these values were

528 calculated using the t-TDI for BPA due to the lack of a specific value for BPS. This
529 highlights the need for further research to establish a t-TDI for BPS and to better
530 understand the risks associated with bee pollen consumption.

531

532 **4. Conclusions**

533 In this study, an analytical methodology has been developed and validated for the
534 simultaneous determination of fourteen BPs residues in bee pollen. Two efficient sample
535 treatments were proposed, based on the QuEChERS and SUPRAS methodologies,
536 respectively, which present a similar performance and, in some cases, better than the only
537 previous treatment published. QuEChERS methodology presents better efficiency when
538 extracting the compounds and reducing the matrix effect, while the SUPRAS
539 methodology is faster, simpler, and requires less reagent consumption. Chromatographic
540 conditions (UHPLC-MS/MS) were selected from previous and recent work from our
541 group. Additionally, a greenness assessment was conducted for both methodologies
542 following three analytical metrics AGREE, AGREEPrep and Complex GAPI. The results
543 obtained from the three studied metrics were consistent, indicating that the developed
544 methodologies could be considered as “green”. SUPRAS demonstrated a slightly better
545 environmental performance than QuEChERS, based on the metrics evaluated,
546 particularly in terms of solvent waste and sample treatment miniaturization. However,
547 both methodologies still present environmental challenges, especially regarding
548 instrumentation and energy consumption. Further improvements in automation and
549 reducing environmental penalties associated with UHPLC-MS/MS could enhance their
550 sustainability profiles. The proposed methods were validated, and the results showed that
551 the analytical performance of both procedures was good. Indeed, LOQs were significantly
552 lower than the SMLs established by the European Commission and the values reported

553 in previous studies. However, the QuEChERS method demonstrated better results in
554 terms of sensitivity (low LODs and LOQs), matrix effect (absence of a significant matrix
555 effect) and trueness (slightly higher recovery percentages). Finally, thirty bee pollen
556 samples from different Spanish regions were analyzed with the QuEChERS-based
557 method, and the results revealed the presence of residues of three (BPM, BPP, and BPS)
558 in twelve of the samples. However, only BPS was quantified in the samples but at
559 concentrations lower than the established SML. Finally, regarding human food safety, the
560 EDI values assessed for BPS in the samples were higher than the oral reference dose
561 recommended by the EFSA. The THQ and HI values were above 1 in all cases, indicating
562 a potential carcinogenic health risk. However, these data were calculated using the
563 established BPA values, due to the lack of a specific value for BPS. This underscores the
564 need for further research in this area.

565

566 **Abbreviations**

567 **AF**, samples spiked after sample treatment; **AGREE**, analytical greenness calculator; **BF**,
568 samples spiked before sample treatment; **BP**, bisphenol; **BPA**, bisphenol A; **BPAF**,
569 bisphenol AF; **BPAP**, bisphenol AP; **BPB**, bisphenol B; **BPBP**, bisphenol BP; **BPC**,
570 bisphenol C; **BPE**, bisphenol E, **BPF**, bisphenol F; **BPFL**, bisphenol FL; **BPM**, bisphenol
571 M; **BPP**, bisphenol P; **BPPH**, bisphenol PH; **BPS**, bisphenol S; **BPZ**, bisphenol Z; **BW**,
572 body weight; **CI**, concentration intake; **DAD**, diode array detector; **DI**, dietary intake;
573 **EDI**, estimated daily intake; **EFSA**, European Food Safety Authority; **FLD**, fluorescence
574 detector; **GAC**, green analytical principles; **GAPI**, green analytical procedure index; **HI**,
575 hazard index; **HPLC**, high-performance liquid chromatography; **HQ**, hazard quotient;
576 **IS**, internal standard; **LOD**, limit of detection; **LOQ**, limit of quantification; **m/z**, mass-

577 to-charge; **MS**, mass spectrometry; **MS/MS**; tandem mass spectrometry; **QuEChERS**,
578 quick, easy, cheap, effective, rugged, and safe; **R²**, determination coefficient; **RfD**,
579 reference dose; **RSD**, relative standard deviation; **SCI**, slope confidence interval; **SMLs**,
580 specific migration limits; **SUPRAS**, supramolecular solvents; **t-TDI**, temporary tolerable
581 daily intake value; **THQ**; target hazard quotient, **UHPLC**; ultra-high-performance liquid
582 chromatography; **μ-SOA-MSPD**, micro salting-out assisted matrix solid-phase
583 dispersion.

584

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592

593 **Conflict of interest**

594 The authors of this manuscript declare no conflict of interest.

595

596 **Data availability**

597 The datasets generated during the current study are included in this published article, or
598 they are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

599

600 **CRedit AUTHORSHIP CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT**

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736 **Figure captions**

737 **Figure 1.-** Schemes of the proposed analytical procedures: **A)** SUPRAS and **B)**
738 QuEChERS.

739 **Figure 2.-** Representative UHPLC-MS/MS chromatograms (MRM mode using the
740 quantification transitions; see **Table 2**) obtained from **A)** blank (analyte free) bee pollen
741 sample, and **B)** blank bee pollen sample spiked with the selected BPs at medium level (50
742 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) level. Bee pollen samples were treated with the proposed QuEChERS procedure.
743 (Note: intensity of detected ions represented in cps, counts per second)

Figure 1

A) SUPRAS

B) QuEChERS

STEP 1: Extraction

STEP 2: Clean-up

Figure 2

Table 1.- Calibration curve data, LOD, LOQ and SML values.

Compounds	Standard in solvent		SUPRAS				QuEChERS				SML (µg/kg)
	SCI	R ²	SCI	R ²	LOD	LOQ	SCI	R ²	LOD	LOQ	
BPA	0.16 ± 0.01	0.992	0.10 ± 0.01	0.995	6.0	19.0	0.16 ± 0.01	0.996	4.2	14.0	50
BPAF	1.90 ± 0.02	0.993	1.87 ± 0.03	0.997	3.0	9.5	1.93 ± 0.04	0.997	0.9	2.9	NS
BPAP	1.20 ± 0.34	0.997	1.08 ± 0.25	0.999	2.4	7.1	1.14 ± 0.30	0.999	0.3	1.0	NS
BPB	0.17 ± 0.03	0.994	0.15 ± 0.02	0.991	2.3	7.8	0.18 ± 0.02	0.993	1.4	4.8	NS
BPBP	0.82 ± 0.12	0.993	0.76 ± 0.10	0.996	2.6	7.0	0.80 ± 0.09	0.994	0.8	2.7	NS
BPC	0.01 ± 0.002	0.994	0.01 ± 0.001	0.997	6.8	22.4	0.01 ± 0.002	0.997	4.0	13.3	NS
BPE	0.25 ± 0.03	0.994	0.16 ± 0.02	0.992	1.9	6.3	0.21 ± 0.03	0.994	0.9	2.8	NS
BPF	0.05 ± 0.01	0.999	0.03 ± 0.01	0.991	4.5	15.0	0.04 ± 0.01	0.993	3.1	10.4	NS
BPFL	2.02 ± 0.15	0.999	1.92 ± 0.25	0.996	4.7	16.0	1.95 ± 0.31	0.992	2.2	7.3	NS
BPM	0.42 ± 0.01	0.999	0.27 ± 0.01	0.997	2.0	6.7	0.43 ± 0.01	0.999	1.2	3.9	NS
BPP	0.44 ± 0.07	0.995	0.43 ± 0.06	0.996	1.5	4.8	0.43 ± 0.10	0.997	0.8	2.8	NS
BPPH	0.37 ± 0.03	0.991	0.24 ± 0.02	0.993	1.9	6.2	0.33 ± 0.04	0.995	1.5	5.0	NS
BPS	5.10 ± 0.60	0.998	3.1 ± 0.30	0.997	0.6	2.1	4.50 ± 0.30	0.999	0.4	1.2	50
BPZ	0.38 ± 0.02	0.999	0.36 ± 0.02	0.996	4.0	13.0	0.37 ± 0.01	0.991	2.8	9.4	NS

LOD, limit of detection; **LOQ**, limit of quantification; **NS**, not specified; **R²**, determination coefficient; **SCI***, slope confident intervals ($\times 10^{-2}$); **SML**, specific migration limit.

Table 2.- List of MRMs and mass spectrometry instrumental conditions for the target analytes and the internal standard.

Compound	Q1	Q3	Dwell	DP	EP	CE	CXP
			time (ms)	(volts)	(volts)	(volts)	(volts)
BPA	227.0	210.9 ^Q	20	-60	-10	-24	-18
	227.0	133.0 ^C	20	-40	-10	-34	-15
	227.0	117.0 ^C	20	-40	-10	-64	-13
IS (BPA-d16)	241.1	222.0 ^Q	20	-45	-10	-28	-11
	241.1	141.9 ^C	20	-45	-10	-40	-21
	241.1	97.9 ^C	20	-45	-10	-60	-5
BPAF	334.9	264.9 ^Q	20	-185	-10	-28	-18
	334.9	196.9 ^C	20	-40	-10	-52	-11
	334.9	176.8 ^C	20	-40	-10	-62	-11
BPAP	289.0	274.0 ^Q	20	-95	-10	-32	-27
	289.0	211.0 ^C	20	-80	-10	-36	-13
	289.0	195.1 ^C	20	-80	-10	-36	-11
BPB	241.0	210.9 ^Q	20	-15	-6	-40	-8
	241.0	224.8 ^C	20	-45	-10	-24	-21
	241.0	147.0 ^C	20	-45	-10	-34	-7
BPBP	351.0	273.0 ^Q	20	-60	-10	-36	-9
	351.0	283.1 ^C	20	-70	-10	-28	-9
	351.0	253.3 ^C	20	-70	-10	-36	-5
BPC	255.1	238.9 ^Q	20	-30	-10	-15	-7
	255.1	223.0 ^C	20	-55	-10	-28	-7
	255.1	147.0 ^C	20	-55	-10	-18	-13
BPE	212.9	197.9 ^Q	20	-55	-10	-24	-17
	212.9	118.8 ^C	20	-45	-10	-32	-13
	212.9	92.9 ^C	20	-45	-10	-30	-11
BPF	198.9	92.9 ^Q	20	-80	-10	-30	-11
	198.9	104.9 ^Q	20	-60	-10	-30	-9
	198.9	77.0 ^C	20	-60	-10	-32	-9
BPFL	349.0	255.8 ^Q	20	-55	-10	-36	-31
	349.0	79.9 ^C	20	-55	-10	-78	-37
	349.0	281.2 ^C	20	-55	-10	-26	-17
BPM	345.0	329.9 ^Q	12	-150	-10	-38	-21
	345.0	251.6 ^C	12	-150	-10	-38	-21
	345.0	132.9 ^C	12	-150	-10	-48	-17
BPP	345.0	329.9 ^Q	20	-30	-13	-60	-25
	345.0	315.0 ^C	20	-135	-10	-38	-13
	345.0	133.0 ^C	20	-135	-10	-48	-9
BPPH	379.0	208.9 ^Q	12	-120	-10	-48	-17
	379.0	364.0 ^C	12	-120	-10	-34	-15
	379.0	192.9 ^C	12	-120	-10	-90	-11
BPS	248.9	108.0 ^Q	20	-90	-10	-36	-10
	248.9	92.0 ^C	20	-65	-10	-50	-11
	248.9	155.9 ^C	20	-65	-10	-30	-9
BPZ	267.0	173.0 ^Q	20	-60	-10	-36	-20
	267.0	224.0 ^C	20	-55	-10	-36	-31
	267.0	197.0 ^C	20	-55	-10	-36	-31

^Q, quantification; ^C, confirmation; **CE**, collision energy; **CXP**, collision cell exit potential; **DP**, entry orifice potential; **ID**, identification; **Q_n**, Mass of pseudo-ion "n".

Table 3.- Evaluation of the extraction efficiency (recovery percentages \pm %RSD) of the sample treatment and the matrix effect (mean values \pm %RSD). Data obtained as described in Sections 2.2, 3.3 and Table 4S, and the results were obtained from three replicates that were injected in triplicate.

Compounds	SUPRAS						QuEChERS					
	EE			ME			EE			ME		
	LL	ML	HL	LL	ML	HL	LL	ML	HL	LL	ML	HL
BPA	81 \pm 10	85 \pm 8	82 \pm 11	-39 \pm 9	-33 \pm 5	-36 \pm 3	107 \pm 6	105 \pm 2	104 \pm 3	1 \pm 8	5 \pm 11	2 \pm 9
BPAF	92 \pm 6	91 \pm 9	87 \pm 5	0 \pm 11	+3 \pm 8	-5 \pm 9	97 \pm 5	92 \pm 5	94 \pm 4	-6 \pm 6	0 \pm 7	+5 \pm 6
BPAP	92 \pm 13	89 \pm 9	85 \pm 8	-7 \pm 10	-10 \pm 7	-12 \pm 6	90 \pm 2	94 \pm 7	86 \pm 7	4 \pm 6	-6 \pm 3	-2 \pm 3
BPB	82 \pm 6	81 \pm 2	85 \pm 4	-12 \pm 4	-13 \pm 3	-12 \pm 6	101 \pm 8	98 \pm 7	95 \pm 6	+6 \pm 4	-2 \pm 3	+4 \pm 3
BPBP	100 \pm 8	96 \pm 9	99 \pm 8	-1 \pm 7	-8 \pm 4	-9 \pm 4	96 \pm 3	101 \pm 5	96 \pm 4	+1 \pm 6	-5 \pm 8	-7 \pm 9
BPC	81 \pm 9	86 \pm 10	83 \pm 7	-10 \pm 9	-15 \pm 4	-17 \pm 3	92 \pm 3	93 \pm 2	91 \pm 4	-13 \pm 4	-9 \pm 2	-8 \pm 4
BPE	86 \pm 3	84 \pm 2	82 \pm 5	-37 \pm 9	-36 \pm 5	-31 \pm 8	79 \pm 2	76 \pm 4	78 \pm 5	-18 \pm 4	-16 \pm 6	-17 \pm 5
BPF	96 \pm 6	90 \pm 5	91 \pm 2	-40 \pm 5	-43 \pm 4	-37 \pm 6	78 \pm 8	86 \pm 7	80 \pm 7	-15 \pm 7	-17 \pm 8	-13 \pm 7
BPFL	103 \pm 12	97 \pm 9	96 \pm 10	-4 \pm 6	-8 \pm 7	-11 \pm 9	99 \pm 11	103 \pm 6	97 \pm 7	-4 \pm 8	-8 \pm 7	-11 \pm 4
BPM	87 \pm 10	91 \pm 7	89 \pm 9	-24 \pm 9	-21 \pm 6	-26 \pm 8	114 \pm 3	106 \pm 4	109 \pm 6	-5 \pm 7	-1 \pm 5	-7 \pm 8
BPP	84 \pm 11	89 \pm 7	85 \pm 5	-5 \pm 9	-8 \pm 7	-7 \pm 6	95 \pm 3	96 \pm 5	91 \pm 7	-1 \pm 5	+2 \pm 4	-4 \pm 6
BPPH	77 \pm 9	82 \pm 5	75 \pm 7	-39 \pm 5	-38 \pm 6	-36 \pm 8	103 \pm 8	99 \pm 4	102 \pm 8	-8 \pm 8	-13 \pm 7	-15 \pm 9
BPS	71 \pm 6	77 \pm 2	72 \pm 2	-45 \pm 6	-38 \pm 7	-40 \pm 6	79 \pm 5	75 \pm 7	77 \pm 7	-18 \pm 6	-14 \pm 7	-16 \pm 8
BPZ	80 \pm 10	83 \pm 9	81 \pm 6	-1 \pm 8	-3 \pm 6	-4 \pm 9	96 \pm 4	92 \pm 4	97 \pm 5	-6 \pm 7	-2 \pm 8	-8 \pm 5

EE, extraction efficiency; ME, matrix effect; LL, low level (LOQ, see Table 1); ML, medium level (50 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$); HL, high level (250 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$).

Table 4.- Assessment of the proposed sample treatments sustainability using analytical greenness calculator (AGREE), analytical GREENness (AGREEPrep) metric, and complex green analytical procedure index (ComplexGAPI).

Metric tool	SUPRAS	QuEChERS
AGREE		
AGREEPrep		
ComplexGAPI		

Table 5.- Results (means of triplicate analyses ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$); %RSD < 15% in all cases) of the investigation of the studied BPs in bee pollen. The other BPs under study were below LOD in the samples. LODs and LOQs are summarized in **Table 1**.

Sample	BPS	BPP	BPM
E1	6.5	<LOD	<LOD
E2	<LOD	<LOD	<LOQ
E5	6.5	<LOQ	<LOQ
E6	5.9	<LOD	<LOD
C1	5.3	<LOD	<LOD
C2	4.6	<LOD	<LOD
C3	6.5	<LOD	<LOD
C4	6.0	<LOD	<LOD
C5	5.4	<LOD	<LOD
C6	5.5	<LOD	<LOD
C7	5.7	<LOD	<LOD
C8	6.4	<LOD	<LOD
C9	4.9	<LOD	<LOD
C12	<LOQ	<LOD	<LOD